
What's a toxic environment for a PhD student?

Prospective PhD students might not fully grasp the importance of selecting the right host lab and could find themselves in the wrong lab or institutional setting. Being aware of potential red flags is crucial. Here are some issues I've witnessed over the years.

Hyper-competitive environment

While a certain degree of competition can be stimulating, overly competitive labs where students do not support one another can hinder personal and collective growth. There are instances where new students are relegated to supporting roles, mainly aiding in the research and thesis work of others, which can stifle their own academic development. Hyper-competitive labs where collaboration and communication are lacking can lead to a sense of isolation, which is particularly detrimental as science thrives on intellectual exchange and teamwork.

Sink or swim supervision

In the challenging journey of a PhD, an engaged supervisor is crucial. PhD students with absent supervisors face a “sink or swim” situation, lacking critical guidance and support. Without regular feedback, mentorship, and academic engagement, students may feel isolated and overwhelmed, struggling to advance their projects or integrate into the broader academic community.

[What to Look for in a Good Mentor.](#)

Lack of transparency

Some labs and institutions practice top-down decision-making without clarity or justification, undermining a culture of respect. Students might find themselves following inexplicable directives, such as a PI who instructs not to present any experiments until they are replicated

three times. A lack of transparency can lead to misunderstandings, misaligned expectations, and a lack of trust between students and supervisors.

Lack of work-life balance

Labs that expect students to work incessantly, including nights and weekends, without recognizing the need for downtime, can lead to burnout and mental health issues. A caring PI demands dedication and intellectual engagement but also helps the student identify their optimal work-life balance.

PI rewards “Deliveroo” students

In some labs, the culture fosters a dynamic where students who produce desired results are favored, regardless of quality of the work or even research integrity. If you find yourself in such an environment, seek a healthier academic setting as soon as you can.

[Don't be a “deliveroo” student.](#)

Publication expectations

It's concerning if a lab does not anticipate students to publish, especially as first authors. Some PIs consolidate data from several PhD students before considering publication. This approach can demotivate students and leave them feeling exploited rather than mentored. PhD students from such labs will be at a disadvantage compared to students who publish their work.

KamounLab · Sep 20, 2023

People, not papers? A good mentor guides students to publish their work

A nurturing academic mentor prioritizes the growth and development of students, but that shouldn't come at the expense of publishing. An...

[People, not papers? How about people and papers, any papers.](#)

Questionable authorship decisions

While authorship norms can vary, fairness is paramount. Be wary of PIs who allocate authorship based on internal politics, nepotism, or whims, undermining meritocracy and ethical standards. When students contributions to publications are overlooked or undervalued, morale and motivation will be affected.

KamounLab · Dec 15, 2022

Authorship — Let's talk about it!

In academia, authorship can be a touchy subject that is all too easy to sidestep. However, it's always simpler to have a contentious conversation prior to submission. Cite as: Kamoun, S. (2022)....

[Make sure to talk about authorship with your supervisor and understand how they approach it.](#)

Reluctance to preprint

Despite the growing acceptance of preprints in the scientific community, some PIs remain sceptical. For early-career researchers, preprints can significantly enhance their visibility and career prospects, contrasting with the established norms some PIs still cling to. A couple of preprints on your CV may very well end up making the difference in whether you get the fellowship or job.

KamounLab · Nov 30, 2022

Herding cats — How to get biologists to preprint

Managing academics is like herding cats. However, funding agencies — if they wish to — have the power to herd the academic cats and drive them to embrace open science and early sharing of research findings...

[Make sure you join a lab that embraces preprinting. This could impact your career prospects.](#)

OPS (Obsessive Publishing Syndrome)

Be cautious of academic environments dominated by the relentless pursuit of “high-impact” publications at any cost. Look for more balanced settings where contributions to academia, community service, and broader societal engagement are valued. These are generally

nurturing environments that foster personal and academic growth compared to those that suffer from OPS (Obsessive Publishing Syndrome).

Spoel Lab
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[blackinplantscience.org](#)

Black in Plant Science UK @BlackInPlantSci · Mar 16, 2023

Exciting news!!

Today we are launching Black in Plant Science UK – a network to connect, celebrate, and cultivate Black Plant Scientists based in the UK

...

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[Academics involved in activism and community service create a nurturing environment that fosters personal and academic growth.](#)

PI's indifference to your career

A supportive PI should take an interest in your career aspirations. Lack of guidance or interest in your future, exemplified by a PI who neglects to engage in career discussions or even shows feigned interest in their student's prospects, can be detrimental. There are PhD supervisors who have never engaged in career discussions with their students. There is this one PI who neglected to attend their student's viva or to follow up with a call or message afterward. At a minimum, students should anticipate a basic level of empathy from their supervisors.

KamounLab · Jun 26, 2023

Cultivating empathy in academic collaborations

"I believe empathy is the most essential quality of civilization." – Roger Ebert This post was inspired by behavior I witnessed a few days ago at the conference hotel I was staying at. You know those moments whe...

[Sociopaths—essentially self-centered people lacking empathy—are found in academia just as they are in society at large.](#)

History of questionable integrity

The reputation of a lab matters. Engaging with a group known for dubious practices risks your work's credibility and your future in the field. Would you want to publish a bad or worse fake paper? Would you want to be party to the next scandal?

[When the controls are missing but the PI and everyone in the lab is celebrating how amazing the results are...](#)

To conclude...

Being aware of these potential pitfalls can help you make informed decisions about your PhD journey, aiming for a nurturing and ethically sound research environment.

Note to PIs: Addressing the issues above and fostering an inclusive, supportive, and respectful environment is essential for the success and well-being of your PhD students.

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Suggested readings

11 tips for choosing the right PhD

<https://thebiologist.rsb.org.uk/biologist-opinion/11-tips-for-choosing-the-right-phd-for-your-career>

KamounLab in Age of Awareness · Jun 5

Four timeless principles of success

The legacy of my great-grandfather Mohamed Said Kamoun lives on. His principles transcend generations and serve as guiding lights for anyone seeking success, whether in business or personal life. A rece...

[Four timeless principles of success.](#)

KamounLab · May 31

Embracing the journey — Avoid being an energy vampire

“Please enjoy the journey” — let’s etch these words onto the walls of our laboratories. I have always been a sports enthusiast. There’s...

[Embracing the journey.](#)

KamounLab · Jul 26, 2022

Even in a great orchestra, you will only hear the bad player

To be a successful scientist, a balanced skill set is important. Overachievers in just one area will struggle in academia. Cite as:...

[Even in a great orchestra, you will only hear the bad player.](#)

KamounLab · Jun 6, 2022

Time management for academics— forget about the Eisenhower method

I recently came to realize that I don't follow the famed Eisenhower method for time management. Instead, I like to Shuffle. Let me tell y...

	URGENT	NOT URGENT
IMPORTANT	Quadrant I urgent and important DO	Quadrant II not urgent but important PLAN
NOT IMPORTANT	Quadrant III urgent but not important DELEGATE	Quadrant IV not urgent and not important ELIMINATE

[Time management for academics.](#)

KamounLab · Jan 25, 2022

Don't hyperspecialize, you rarely know what will be useful in the future

These questions come up a lot. What should I study? What should I learn? My answer: anything. Cite as: Kamoun, S. (2022). Don't...

[Don't hyperspecialize.](#)

[PI vs. PhD student, or is it the other way around?](#)